

Some Aspects of Aromatic and Medicinal Plants[†]

D. S. BHAKUNI

President, Indian Chemical Society

Plant cells are highly sophisticated chemical factories where a large variety of chemical compounds are manufactured with great precision and ease from simple raw materials at normal temperature and pressure. Plants are thus a very important renewable source of raw materials for the production of a large variety of chemicals.

Because of its vast and wide variation in soil and climate, the Indian subcontinent is suitable for cultivation of a large number of medicinal and aromatic plants which can be used as raw materials for pharmaceutical, perfumery, cosmetics, flavour and food and agrochemical industries. A large number of these plants grow wild and exploited specially for use in indigenous pharmaceutical houses. Some of these plants produce valuable drugs which have high export potential.

Plants can be classified on the basis of their morphological characters. A chemotaxonomical classification of plants based on the types of chemical compounds they produce is more useful. Basic information such as the types of chemical compounds a particular plant produce, their chemical structure and their chemical and biological properties are important for better utilisation of plants. There are several factors that affect the yield of product in the plant. These are, the part of the plant, the age of the plant, time of harvesting and ecological variation.

Success of phytochemical based industry depends to a large extent on the selection of plants of commercial value. It is important to have data on their natural abundance, authenticity, cultivation and agrotechnology. The direct utilization of a plant material is a feature of traditional remedies. Preparations of decoctions, tinctures, galenicals and extracts of plants form a part of many pharmacopoeias of the world. The current trend of medicinal plants based drug industry is to procure standardized extracts of plants as raw materials.

Aromatic plants

A large number of aromatic plants produce essential oils of commerce. In India the essential oil industry was traditionally a cottage industry. Since 1947, a number of industrial houses have been established for commercial production of essential oils, oleoresins and perfumes. The essential oils that are being produced in India include ajowain oil, cedarwood oil, celery oil, citronella oil, davana oil, eucalyptus oil, geranium oil, lavender oil, lemongrass oil, mentha oil, palmarosa oil, patchouli oil, rose oil, sandalwood oil, turpentine oil and vetiver oil. The manufacture of turpen-

tine oil, and resin from pines is a sizeable and well established industry in India having 10000 to 35000 tonnes annual production of the oil. α -Pinene and Δ^3 -carenone are the two important components produced from the oil. α -Ionone from lemongrass oil for perfumery and β -ionone for vitamin A synthesis are produced in India. Before 1960, menthol was not produced in India but the introduction of Japanese mint, *Mentha arvensis* and subsequent improvements thereupon enabled India to produce over 500 tonnes of menthol per year.

Annual world production of limonene is 50000 tonnes. Brazil is the biggest producer of limonene in the world. It is a by-product of citrus industry. Though turpentine oil and eucalyptus oil also yield limonene but the best and economically cheap raw material in the orange and lemon peel which is being used by Brazilian phytochemical industry. In India this source has not yet been tapped for limonene production.

Medicinal plants

Medicinal plants are the source of phytopharmaceuticals. Before independence, the production of plant based modern drugs was confined only to quinine from cinchona bark in three state-owned factories. The first phytochemical industry for quinine was established by the then British Government at Mungpoo in Darjeeling. During the past three and a half decades bulk production of plant-based drugs has become an important segment of Indian pharmaceutical industry. Some of the phytopharmaceuticals which are being produced in India at present are : morphine, codeine, papaverine, thebaine, emetine, quinine, quinidine, digoxin, caffeine, hyoscyne, hyoscyamine, xanthotoxin, psoralen, colchicine, rutin, berberine, vinblastine, vincristine, nicotine, strychnine, brucine, ergot alkaloids, senna glycosides, pyrethroids, podophyllotoxin resin etc.

Phytopharmaceuticals for which technology has been developed for commercial production are : L-dopa from *Mucuna* beans, ajmaline and ajmalicine from *Rauwolfia serpentina* and *Catharanthus* roots respectively, and acetylglycyrrhetic acid from *Glycyrrhiza glabra*.

Commercial plants

Although the number of medicinal and aromatic plants which are being exploited in Indian subcontinent is fairly large. Some of the plants of significant commercial value are :

Papaver somniferum Linn. (opium poppy) :

P. somniferum, a source of opium alkaloids, is one of the most important medicinal plant cultivated in India. At present approximately 22800 hectares are under cultivation and about 865 tonnes of opium is produced. Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (CIMAP), Lucknow, has carried out considerable research and developmental work on opium poppy and has developed improved agronomic practices. Two new varieties 'Shyma' and 'Shweta' have been developed and released by the Institute. These new varieties give 50% higher yield than the old varieties. The Institute is now concentrating on development of those varieties which will have higher quantity of alkaloids in straw, so that India can switch over to new technology for production of alkaloids from straw.

Hyoscyamus species :

Three tropane alkaloids producing plants which are being cultivated in India are common henbane (*Hyoscyamus niger*), Egyptian henbane (*Hyoscyamus muticus*) and Australian corkwood (*Duboisia myoporoides*). *H. niger* (common black henbane) produces hyoscyne and hyoscyamine. The plant is used mainly for the production of 'Hyoscyamus extract' and is cultivated on a very limited scale in Madhya Pradesh and parts of Uttar Pradesh for production of 'Hyoscyamus tincture'. CIMAP has developed a new yellow-flowering mutant which gives twice the yield of alkaloids.

Hyoscyamus muticus (Egyptian henbane) was introduced by CIMAP, Lucknow, about 10 years ago. It is cultivated on a limited scale for production of hyoscyamine and atropine. The Institute has developed a new variety designated as NP-41 which gives approximately 1% total alkaloids and more than 1.5 tonnes herb per acre. Necessary agrotechnology as well as processing technology have been worked out by the Institute for the cultivation of plant and production of alkaloids of interest.

Duboisia myoporoides (Australian corkwood tree), a source of the alkaloids, hyoscyne, hyoscyamine and atropine, was introduced in India by CIMAP, about 10 years ago from Australia. Agrotechnology for its cultivation as well as processing technology for production of hyoscyne, hyoscyamine and atropine have been developed by the Institute. Some new better varieties of the plant are being evolved.

Catharanthus roseus (common periwinkle) is the main source of Vinca alkaloids. India is one of the few countries in the world which cultivated this plant. Most of its production is exported to European countries. The plant is cultivated in approximately 1000 hectares mainly in the states of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Maharashtra. CIMPA's regional centre at Bangalore has developed agrotechnology for cultivation of this plant. A tetraploid variety, which is not only high yielding but also resistant to diseases has

been evolved. Vincristine and vinblastine, the two valuable drugs for treatment for certain forms of cancer are being produced by CIPLA, from this plant. A limited amount of roots and leaves are processed in India for production of ajmalicine for export.

Rauvolfia serpentina :

The main source of Rauvolfia alkaloids of commerce is *R. serpentina*. Most of the requirement of industry of the plant is met from wild sources. Only limited quantity of roots are being cultivated. Crude extracts as well as reserpine is obtained from the plant. A limited amount of alkaloids is exported.

Cinchona alkaloids :

India is one of the major producers of cinchona and cinchona alkaloids. Approximately 20 to 30 tonnes of cinchona alkaloids are being produced annually mainly for internal consumption. Indian plantations are located in Northern and Western Bengal and hills of Tamil Nadu.

Cephaelis ipecacuanh :

In India ipecac alkaloids are obtained from *C. ipecacuanh*. India is one of the few countries in the world which produces ipecac roots. Its cultivation is confined to Darjeeling District in West Bengal under the department of Cinchona and other Medicinal Plants. About 7 to 10 tonnes of roots are produced annually for the production of emetine for internal consumption and export.

Ergot alkaloids :

About 15 to 20 tonnes of crude Ergot is produced in the country annually from *Claviceps purpurea*.

Dioscorea species :

In India most of the supply of diosgenin is obtained from *Dioscorea deltoidea* which grows wild in the hilly area of Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh. Approximately 400 to 600 tonnes of roots of the wild species of the plant are exploited in these states for production of approximately 20 tonnes of diosgenin. CIMAP has developed agrotechnology for cultivation of *D. deltoidea* and two American species *D. composita* and *D. floribunda*. Agrotechnology for cultivation of crop is available in the country. CIMAP and some other Institutes have developed tissue culture methods for multiplication of elite clones. Two new clones having 6% diosgenin has developed by CIMAP.

Cassia angustifolia :

C. angustifolia (Indian senna) the source of sennosides, is one of the important export item of India. The crop is cultivated in approximately 2500 to 3000 hectares of land in the state of Tamil Nadu and about 2500-3000 tonnes of senna leaves and pods are produced. Major part of the production is exported to Europe. Some of the production is converted into sennosides for internal consumption and export. Efforts are being made at CIMAP to develop better

and high yielding varieties of senna.

Ammi majus :

Xanthotoxin is obtained from *A. majus*. CIMAP has developed agrotechnology for cultivation of the plant and production of xanthotoxin.

Plantago ovata (Pyllium seed) :

Approximately 26000 to 27000 hectares of land are under cultivation of this crop with annual turn over of about 18000 to 19000 tonnes of seed and husk. Most of its production is exported and earning of about Rs. 16 to 20 crores is made. Improved agrotechnology for the cultivation of the crop has been developed by Gujarat Agricultural University.

Wild plants of commerce

Over 200 wild plants are exploited in the country for making formulations of traditional remedies. Some of these plants are also used for production of drugs used in modern system of medicine. The most important plants exploited for production of drugs are : *Strychnos nux vomica* for production of strychnine and brucine, *Berberis spp.* for berberine, and *Gloriosa superba* for colchicine.

Podophyllum emodi, *Valeriana wallichii* and *Adhatoda vasica* are exploited for the production of *Podophyllum* extract, *Valeriana* extract and *Adhatoda* extract respectively.

Aromatic plants of commerce

Several essential oil bearing plants of commerce are cultivated and processed in the country for internal consumption and export and more than 25 essential oils are produced.

Menthol and mint oil :

These are obtained from *Mentha arvensis* (Japanese mint), *M. piperita* (pepper mint), *M. spicata* (sepearmint), *M. cardiaca* (scotch mint), *M. citrata* (bergamot mint). Agrotechnology for the cultivation of these plants have been developed by Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (CIMAP), Lucknow. At present India is producing approximately 800 tonnes of mint oil and 400 tonnes of menthol annually, mainly in Uttar Pradesh, Haryana and Punjab. CIMAP has released two new high-yielding varieties of *M. arvensis* which give the highest percentage of mint oil and menthol. These two varieties are MAS-1 and CIMAP hybrid-77. These varieties have replaced the original Japanese clone. India is now exporting menthol to developed countries.

Lemongrass oil :

It was being produced in India for over 100 years from *Cymbopogon flenuosus* which grows wild in Kerala. CIMAP has developed agrotechnology for cultivation of the plant. A new high-yielding variety, LS-48, having 50% higher yield of herb and oil, than the wild variety, has been evolved

by CIMAP. Production of lemongrass oil in India has gone down because of decrease in wild growth of the plant in Kerala as a result of indiscriminate exploitation and deforestation. CIMAP has identified a clone of *C. flenuosus* with 80% geraniol. A new clone of *C. pendulus* has also been identified which gives oil containing more than 85% citral. Better varieties of lemongrass having higher oil content are being evolved at CIMAP.

Palmarosa oil :

It is being produced in India, from *Cymbopogon martini* (Palmarosa), wild variety, mainly in Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra for the last 50 years. CIMAP has developed necessary agrotechnology for the cultivation of the plant. A high yielding variety of *C. martini* has been developed.

Sandalwood oil :

It is produced from *Santalum album*. India is the major producer of sandalwood oil in the world. At one time the annual production of sandalwood oil in the country was approximately 200 tonnes. The production of the oil in the country at present has gone down below 30 tonnes annually because of indiscriminate exploitation of the plant from wild source and increase in production of the oil in other countries such as Indonesia and Fiji.

Eucalyptus oil :

India produces two types of eucalyptus oil. The cineol type oil is obtained from *Eucalyptus globulus*, mainly from forest plantation in Nilgiri and Palni Hills as a by-product of paper and pulp industry. The second type of oil is produced from *E. citriodora*, mainly in the states of Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Kerala. Total production of eucalyptus oil in the country is approximately 50 tonnes annually. Some of the cineol type oil is exported.

Vetiver oil :

Vetiver oil in India was being produced in limited amount for over 100 years. Most of the vetiver oil is still produced from wild growth of *Vetiveria zizanioides*. CIMAP has developed necessary agrotechnology for the crop on marginal, sub-marginal soils and riverbeds and has evolved a high yielding variety.

Geranium oil :

It is produced from *Pelargonium graveolens* which was introduced in India in 1941. Approximately 20 to 25 tonnes geranium oil is produced in the country.

Celery oil :

India is the major producer of celery seeds. Annually 2000 to 3000 tonnes of the seeds are produced and only a limited quantity is converted into oil (1 to 2 tonnes) for export to Europe and United States.

Davana oil :

It is obtained from *Artemisia pallens* (Davana). A limited amount of davana oil is produced in Karnataka and Tamil Nadu which is exported to Japan and France. Use of

the oil is increasing in the world market. Necessary agrotechnology for cultivation of *A. pallens* has been developed by CIMAP.

Jasmine oil :

It is obtained from *Jasminum grandiflorum* (jasmine). The oil was being produced in old fashioned stills for use in indigenous perfumery for more than 100 years. The industry has been modernised and quality jasmine oil is produced for export.

Rose oil :

Rose oil was being produced from *Rosa damascena* (rose) in old fashion country stills. CIMAP introduced Bulgarian rose in Kashmir Valley and has developed modern technology for distillation of rose oil. Approximately 10 to 15 kg Bulgarian rose oil is produced annually, mainly for internal consumption.

Lavender oil :

It is obtained from *Lavandula officianalis* which was introduced in the country by CIMAP 10 years ago. A new high-yielding variety designated 'Shere Kashmir' was evolved and is being cultivated in Kashmir valley which gives 50 to 60% higher yield of oil than the parent plant.

Patchouli oil :

It is obtained from *Pogostemon patchouli* (patchouli) which was introduced in India in 1940. Necessary agrotechnology for cultivation of the crop was developed by CIMAP.

Some of the essential oils produced on a limited scale in the country from wild plants are : clary sage oil (*Salvia sclarea*), dill oil (*Anethum graveoleus*), nagarmotha oil (*Cyperus scariosus*), French basil (*Ocimum basilium*), German chamomil (*Matricaria chamomilla*), rosemary oil (*Rosemarinus officinalis*), Cedarwood oil (*Cedrus deodara*), *Artemisia vestita* oil, ferula oil (*Ferula jaeschkeana*), juniper leaf oil (*Juniperus communis*).

Import and export of medicinal plants

Several medicinal plants are imported into the country such as *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Lavandula stoechas*, *Smilax ornata*, *S. china*, *Cuscuta epithymum*, *Operculina turpethum*, *Thymus vulgaris* and *Pimpinella anisum* etc.

The medicinal plants exported from the country are : *Plantago ovata* (seeds and husk), *Cassia angustifolia* (rhizome), *Inula racemosa* (rhizome), *Rauwolfia serpentina* (roots), *Hedychium spicatum* (rhizome), *Zingiber officinale* (rhizome), *Colchicum luteum* (rhizome and seeds), *Valeriana wallichii* (rhizome), *Acorus calamus* (rhizome), *Adhatoda vasica* (whole plant), *Juglans regia* (bark), *Punica granatum* (flowers, roots and barks), *Berberis aristata* (roots), *Juniperus communis* (fruits), *J. macropoda* (fruits), *Heracleum candicans* (rhizome), *Picrorhiza hurooa* (roots), *Aconitum* species other than *Heterophyllum* (roots), *Sausurea lappa* (rhizome), *Swertia chirata* (whole plant)

and *Podophyllum emodi* (rhizome).

One of the problems which phytochemical based industries are facing today is the dwindling supply of plant-materials.

Endangered medicinal plants

The medicinal plants that are almost extinct, threatened, greatly threatened and likely to be threatened due to indiscriminate exploitation are : *Aconitum deinorrhizum* (almost extinct), *Aconitum heterophyllum* (greatly threatened), *Angelica glauca*, *Arnebia benthemii*, *Atropa acuminata*, *Berberis aristata*, *Colchicum luteum*, *Dioscorea deltoidea*, *Ferula jaeschkeana*, *Gentiana huroo*, *Nardostachys*, *Jatamansi*, *Orchis latifolia*, *Podophyllum emodi*, *Rheum emodi*, *Swertia chirata* are threatened plants. *Artemisia brevifolia*, *A. maritima*, *Corydalis govaniiana*, *Hedychium spicatum*, *Picrorhiza kurroa*, *Valeriana wallichii* and *Zanthoxylum alatum* are likely to be threatened.

Advantages of plants based industries

The main advantages of the plant based industries are : (i) use of renewable source of raw materials, (ii) low cost investment, (iii) high value products, (iv) labour oriented and (v) best suited for agricultural countries like India. The success of plant-based industries depends if one has authentic information about natural abundance, authenticity, agrotechnology of the plants of commercial value and processing technology. The industry must also have linkages with research institutions, universities, colleges and other organisations which are sources of new knowledge.

Drug development

A country like India is very much suited for development of drugs from medicinal plant. India has a rich heritage of knowledge on plant-based drugs both for use in preventive and curative medicines. Plants form a dominant part of Ayurvedic pharmacopoeia where drugs have been classified on the basis of their physiological action. For example Charak has divided plant drugs into fifty groups according to the actions of their decoctions. Ayurveda was a well organised science of its times. Ayurvedic texts were translated into Greek (300 B.C.), Tibetan and Chinese (300 A.D.), Persian and Arabic (700 A.D.), and other languages of Asian countries.

Strategies of drug discovery

Of the many strategies for selection of plants as a drug source, the most rewarding has been the criteria of their reputation in folklore medicine. For example *Rauwolfia serpentina* provided the hypotensive alkaloids reserpine, rescinnamine and deserpedine; *Digitalis purpurea* and *D. lantana* yielded digitoxin and digoxin, both powerful cardiotonic agents; curare gave the muscle relaxant d-

tubocularine; opium yielded the analgesics codeine and morphine, as well as the antitussive noscapine and smooth muscle relaxant, papaverine; *Atropa belladonna* provided the parasympatholytic atropine, scopolamine and 1-hyoscyamine; *Cinchona* species gave the antimalarial quinine and the antiarrhythmic quinidine; and *Ammi majus* yielded 8-hydroxy-psoralen used for the treatment of leukoderma.

Another strategy of the discovery of new drugs from plants involves the random or discrete selection of plants followed by phytochemical screening to establish the presence of chemical group which are usually present with specific types of biological activity. For example, a number of screening programme have been initiated in search for cardenolides by screening plant samples for the presence of 2-deoxy-sugars or the presence of active methylene groups as present in the C₁₇-unsaturated lactone moiety. Following this approach cardenolides were found to be widely distributed not only in the Scrophulariaceae, Apocynaceae and Asclepidaceae, but in the Compositae, Liliaceae, Moraceae, Solanaceae and Sterculaceae families.

The phytochemical screening of a large number of plants for alkaloids has been quite common. Perhaps more plants have been screened for the presence of steroidal saponins by means of an initial hemolysis test than any other phytochemical group. Other chemical groups that have been involved in this type of research are the flavanoids and related polyphenolic glycosides and isothiocyanates glycosides. With the exception of steroidal saponins, this type of screening programmes have been unsuccessful in the development of new drugs.

Of greater importance but with infinitely more problems is the approach involving screening of randomly selected plants for one or more types of biological activities such as antimicrobial, antiviral, spermicidal, antimalarial, antifertility, hypoglycaemic, and antineoplastic activities.

A broad biological screening of plants is yet another approach in operation at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. About 125 test systems are available for evaluating the biological activities of plants extracts and pure compounds. The tests include antibacterial, antifungal, antileishmanial, anthelmintic, antitape worm, antimalarial, antiviral, antiinflammatory, hypoglycaemic, antihypertensive, choleric, anticholeric, CNS depressant and CNS stimulant activities. CDRI so far has screened over 4000 plant extracts. The plants are collected and identified by a team of botanists. Herbarium sheet of each plant is kept for reference in the herbarium of the Institute. The results of the broad biological screening are published in a series of papers.

The criteria of a good screening programme are that it should be simple, economical, reliable, pick up new unex-

pected or unique activity, unbiased and comprehensive and finally it should have in-built safety mechanisms. The primary screening of an extract is mainly descriptive and qualitative. In-depth evaluation is carried out at the level of secondary screening.

There are several problems associated with broad biological screening of plant extracts. It is well established that in certain plants the active principles are concentrated in a particular part of the plant, i.e. roots, leaves, seeds, fruits etc. In such cases it is expected that one should make the extract of each part of the plant separately for biological evaluation. Further, the concentration of active principles may vary at different stages of growth of the plant or may vary with ecological conditions. To cover all the possibilities one has to make several extracts of the same plant. Increasing number of extracts increases cost and is also time-consuming.

The other major problem of a large-scale biological screening is the selection of a single solvent for the preparation of extracts for biological evaluation in which all active and desirable compounds will be soluble with a minimum of toxic principles. It is generally encountered in the evaluation of crude extracts that certain substances which are present in the plant are extracted in crude extract and prevent the determination of a specific biological activity either through an opposite action or through toxicity and in some other way. This can be exemplified by the fact that the active antineoplastic alkaloid leurocristine was isolated in high yield from crude alkaloidal fraction of *Catharanthus roseus* which were themselves devoid of antitumor activity. A similar phenomenon has been experienced with leurosine an active antitumor agent isolated from crude fractions of *C. lances* that were devoid of activity.

The largest biological screening programme involving plant extracts, isolate and synthetic compounds is conducted by Drug Research and Development Branch (DRD) of the National Cancer Institute (NCL) in United States. DRD screens free of cost any plant material or isolate for any investigator in the world. They require only name of the plant or isolate, the type of extract being supplied, and a sufficient quantity of the extract or isolate for complete evaluation. A 5–10 g quantity of crude extract is usually sufficient, but the amount of pure compound is dependent on its toxicity. DRD has evaluated over 80000 plant extracts, representing some 10000 plant species. Over 1500 of these species have been confirmed as active tumor inhibitors, against one or more tumors.

Several potent anticancer agents have been isolated from plants. Of these vinblastine and vincristine, the two dimeric indole alkaloids isolated from *Vinca rosea* (*Catharanthus roseus* G. Don), a widely cultivated ever-blooming ornamental plant. Although there is a very minor difference in

the chemical structures of vinblastine and vincristine, however, the clinical effects of these differ considerably. Vinblastine is preferred in the treatment of Hodgkin's disease because of its better tolerance. Vincristine is superior to vinblastine in the treatment of lymphosarcoma. The dosage, requirement of both alkaloids differ markedly, the weekly intravenous dose of vinblastine for humans is 0.01–0.2 mg/kg, while that of vincristine is approximately one-tenth of vinblastine. Vincristine shows more neurotoxic effects. Vincristine is considered to have more potency in bone marrow depression. Early symptoms of side-effects are vomiting and fever. Late symptoms are CNS disturbances, alopecia and leukopenia. Since Vinca alkaloids are unable to pass the blood-brain barrier, the side-effects are most probably caused by the metabolites of these drugs.

Both vinblastine and vincristine strongly inactivate pH 5 enzymes and DNA-dependent RNA polymerase and thus interfere markedly with the synthesis of soluble transfer RNA. Vinblastine and vincristine like colchicine and podophylotoxin, cause metaphase arrest. The bases inhibit mitosis *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Thus inhibition results from blockage of metabolic mechanisms caused by biochemical reaction which are not precisely known.

Vinblastine and vincristine are being manufactured in India by CIPLA Ltd., Bombay.

Taxol :

Taxol is the most recent anticancer drug discovered from plant source. It is present in the bark of *Taxus brevifolia* and other *Taxus* species in minute quantities (the sacrifice of a 100 years old tree yielded about 3 kg of bark containing about 300 mg of taxol, about a single dose). The path of the drug from the forest through the laboratory to the patient has been successful because of the perseverance of a cadre of chemists, pharmacologists and oncologists and because of the support of the National Cancer Institute. Although an understanding of taxol's mechanism of action stimulated a great deal of interest, its clinical development has been brought with difficulties. The scarcity of the drug limited its availability for adequate clinical trials, and the hydrophobic nature of the compound made it a continual challenge for formulation chemists, whose goal was to deliver the compound in aqueous solution.

Taxol has now become an important new cancer chemotherapeutic agent, one of the first in a number of years. It has significant activity in drug refractory ovarian cancer, and was approved for the disease by the US Food and Drug Administration in 1992. Other tumors for which taxol has shown activity are cancers of the breast and lung melanoma. Although it holds uncommon promise in the treatment of various cancers, it is not a panacea or a cure for cancer, rather, it is an active drug whose true clinical potential will be realised only with time. Its effectiveness in combination chemo-

therapy, with radiation, with growth factors or as adjuvant chemotherapy in breast cancer remains to be seen.

Other new plant-based drugs :

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, has been involved in the development of new drugs from plants for several years. The new drugs/products, marketed/ready for marketing and under clinical trials are : Gugulipid (hypolipidaemic) from *Commiphora mukul* marketed as guglip to CIPLA Ltd., Bombay, and licensed to Arkopharma Laboratories, France, for its marketing to EEC countries. Isaptent (cervical dilator for medical termination of pregnancy) from *Plantago ovata* (isapgol) seed husk, marketed as Dilex-C to Unichem Laboratories Ltd., Bombay. *Palatable laxative* formulations of *Plantago ovata* (isapgol) seed husk in powder and granule forms open for licensing. Consap cream (spermicidal) from seeds of *Sapindus mukorossi* as a local contraceptive open for licensing. α -Arteether (antimalarial) from *Artemisia annua* for treatment of chloroquine resistant and cerebral malaria is in phase II clinical trials. Bacosides (memory enhancer) from *Bacopa monnii* released in 1996 is being marketed as Memory plus. Picroliv (hepatoprotective) from *Picrorhiza hurooa* is in phase II clinical trials. It has hepatoprotective, cholcretic, anticholestatic, immunostimulant activities and hepatitis B virus neutralising property.

Bioactive alkaloids and their biosynthesis

Bioactive alkaloids :

Alkaloids occupy a unique place in the family of natural products and provide challenging problems for structural elucidation, synthesis and biosynthetic studies. Recognising the importance of alkaloids and alkaloid biosynthesis coupled with our interest in biologically active natural products, my group at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, initiated a study of various aspects of alkaloids of Indian plants which either showed a consistent biological activity when screened or had a reputation in folklore medicine.

A search for hypotensive agent(s) in the active alkaloidal fraction of the alcoholic extract of the leaves and stems of *Croton sparsiflorus* (Euphorbiaceae), a South American plant which has now completely naturalised and grows as a weed in the plains of India, led to the isolation of proaporphines, crotsparine, *N*-methylcrotsparine, *N*,*O*-dimethylcrotsparine, dihydroproaporphine, crotsparinine and *N*-methylcrotsparinine and the known aporphine, sparsiflorine. The structure and stereochemistry of these bases have been assigned. Crotsparine, *N*-methylcrotsparine and *N*-methylcrotsparinine are hypotensive agents. *N*-Methylcrotsparinine produces a sharp but shortlived fall in blood pressure which could be antagonised by atropine to a large extent suggesting thus a cholinergic mechanism of

action. *N*-Methylsparsiflorine methiodide is a potent neuromuscular blocking agent. At 5–10 mg/kg (i.v.) dose in cats it produces 100% blockage of neuromuscular transmission for 30–60 min. Glaziovine, an enantiomer of (*S*)-*N*-methylcrotsparine, is a potent tranquiliser devoid of depressant effects.

In a routine biological screening, a 50% ethanolic extract of *Cocculus pendulus* Diels (Menispermaceae) a shrub which grows in dry parts of North and Western India, displayed hypotensive and anticancer activities. A detailed chemical investigation of the active fraction of the alkaloidal mixture yielded six bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids, namely, pendulin, cocsolin, cocsuline, cocsulinin, pendulinin and pendin. Of these bases pendulin showed hypotensive activity and cocsulinin was found active against cells derived from human carcinoma of the nasopharynx (9 kB).

Cocculus laurifolius DC (Menispermaceae), an evergreen shrub grows in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. A 50% ethanolic extract of the leaves when tested, hypotensive and neuromuscular blocking activities were confirmed. A systematic study of the active fraction of the alcoholic extract led to the isolation of ten new abnormal *Erythrina* alkaloids, isococculidine, isococculine, coccovinine, cocculidinone, and three new dibenz[*d, f*]azonines, laurifonine, laurifine and laurifinine. In addition to these new bases known morphinandienone alkaloid, sebiferine, two proaporphines, stephanine and *N*-methylstephanine, five quaternary aporphines, magnoflorine, laurifoline chlorides, isocorydine, *O*-methylisocorydine, and boldine, methochlorides and 1-benzylisoquinolines, coclaurine, *N*-methylcoclaurine, reticuline and laudanidine. The structure and stereochemistry of the new bases have been determined.

Isococculidine, the major alkaloid of the leaves of *C. laurifolius* displayed neuromuscular blocking and hypotensive activities. Cocculidine and cocculine exhibited hypotensive activity. This activity in these alkaloids has been found due to ganglionic blocking action. The quaternary aporphines, *O*-methylisocorydine, isocorydine, and boldine, methochlorides exhibited d-tubocurarine like curarising action on sciatic skeletal muscles. These quaternary bases also induce hypotensive effects in dogs, cats and rabbits. This activity was found due to considerable ganglionic blocking action on various sympathetic and parasympathetic ganglia.

The roots of *Thalictrum foliolosum* DC (Ranunculaceae), a tall perennial herb, are reported to be used by the natives for the treatment of various ailments. A 50% ethanolic extract of the plant when screened displayed spasmolytic activity. A systematic chemical study of the active alkaloidal mixture gave a new aporphine, *N, O, O*-trimethylsparsiflorine and known bisbenzylisoquinolines, thalidasine and thalrugosidine; benzylisoquinoline

aporphine base, thalicarpine; benzylisoquinoline, reticuline, berberine bases, berberine and palmatine and quaternary aporphine, magnoflorine. Of these bases thalicarpine produced transient hypotensive effects in cats and exhibited significant inhibitory activity against Walker carcinoma 256 in rats. Thalrugosidine displayed antimicrobial activity. Berberine and palmatine exhibited antimicrobial activity against a wide variety of microorganisms including fungi and protozoa.

About 250 *Corydalis* species occur in the Himalayan region and Khasi hills. *C. meifolia*, a perennial herb with underground tubers, is one of these species and grows at an altitude of 12000 to 15000 ft. Extract of *Corydalis* species are reported to be efficacious in many ailments in the Ayurvedic system of medicine. Chemical investigation of *C. meifolia* yielded several alkaloids. Of these octotensine is reported to stimulate isolated guinea pig and rabbit uterus and induces a fall in blood pressure in anaesthetized cats.

Biosynthesis :

The way the living plants make complex molecules from simple building units in a regio- and stereospecific manner is a fascinating area of research. Biosynthetic knowledge helps to rationalise the vast scattered information about various groups of natural products. It also helps in solving structural problems and in designing new synthetic routes to complex natural products.

My group at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, has studied the biosynthesis of 1-benzylisoquinoline alkaloids, reticuline, coclaurine and papaverine; proaporphine alkaloids; crotsparine, *N*-methylcrotsparine and dihydroproaporphine alkaloid crotsparinine, abnormal aporphine alkaloids, nuciferine, sparsiflorine, normal aporphine alkaloid boldine and isocorydine, berberine alkaloids, palmatine, tetra-hydroprotoberberinone, tetrahydro-palmatine; bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids, cocsulinin, cocsuline, benzylisoquinoline-aporphine alkaloid thalicarpine, abnormal *Erythrina* and dibenz[*d, f*]azonine alkaloids. The biosynthesis of phenanthroindolizidine alkaloids tyloporine and tylophorine and of aristolochic acid has been studied by using radio-labelled and optically active precursors. We also determined the structure and absolute configuration of biphenylbisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloids, tiliacorine, tiliacorinine, nortiliacorinine A and B and tiliageine by biosynthetic approach.

Aberrant biosynthesis :

Very little is known about the potentiality of higher plants to carry out transformations on compounds which they do not normally produce. These types of transformation where an 'unnatural precursor' is converted into an 'unnatural product' in living system is called aberrant biosynthesis. This area of research is relatively unexplored in higher plants. A few reported examples of aberrant biosynthesis are the con-

version of 5-fluoronicotinic acid into 5-fluoronicotinine in the tobacco plant (*Nicotiana tabacum*) and conversion of *N*-methyl- Δ' - piperideinium chloride into higher homologue of nicotine.

My group at Central Drug Research Institute, demonstrated bioconversion of 8-bromo- and 8,2'-dibromoreticulines in *Cocculus laurifolius* plant into 1-bromo- and 1,12- dibromotetrahydropalmatine also of 2'-nitro- and 2'-amino reticulines into 12-nitro- and 12-aminotetrahydropalmatine. The experiments thus suggested that many of the enzymes in plants are non-specific and catalyse the biosynthesis of 'unnatural alkaloids' from 'unnatural precursors'.

Concluding remarks

The Indian subcontinent is suitable for cultivation of a large variety of aromatic and medicinal plants which can be used as raw materials for phytochemical-based industries, such as pharmaceutical, perfumery, cosmetics, flavour and food industries.

Indian essential oil industry had been traditionally a cottage industry. Since 1947, a number of industrial houses have been established for commercial production of essential oils, oleoresins and perfumes.

Quinine was the only plant-based drugs manufactured in India before independence. During the past three-and-a-half decade, bulk production of plant-based drugs has become an important segment of Indian pharmaceutical industry.

Medicinal plant-based drug industry was progressing very fast in India but it is now beset with a number of problems. The most serious in the dwindling supply of plant materials from natural sources. However, the problem can be solved by introducing a national policy on medicinal plants with a view to preserve endangered species and to pro-

mote cultivation of plants which are extensively used by industry. Trade in medicinal plants is largely unorganised and uncertain both in demand and price-structure. There is need to have Marketing and Development Board for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants. The Board could interact with the growers on one side and user industries on the other to bring stability in their production, demand, pricing, quality and also could help in international trade.

The chemical investigation of plants has been a favourite area of research in India for several decades. Several distinguished chemists in India have worked on plants. Their contributions to chemistry of natural products have been recognised nationally and internationally. However, most of the work on plants has been of an academic nature with little attempt at biological evaluation of new compounds isolated.

At the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, a team of chemists and biologists have been working in close cooperation with a view to discover therapeutically useful products from plants. The other laboratories which are engaged in developing new drugs or new leads from plant sources are Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu, and some departments of universities and colleges. The important leads which have been obtained are : *Commiphora mukul* (antihypercholesteremic), *Boswellia serrata* (antiarthritic), *Picrorhiza kurroa* (hepatoprotective), *Phyllanthus amarus* (hepatoprotective), *Centella asiatica* (brain tonic), *Cucuma longa* (antiinflammatory), *Andrographis paniculata* (antihepatotoxic), *Withania somnifera* (adaptogen), *Acorus calamus* (tranquilizer), *Sida rhombifolia* (anabolic), *Albizia lebeck* (immunomodulator) and *Valeriana walliachi* (tranquilizer). The aromatic and medicinal plants, the sources of drugs and aromatic chemicals are thus one of the best gifts of nature to mankind.